

Electrode Kinetics of the Reduction of Manganese at the D. M. E. Effect of Cations and Anions on the Mn^{2+}/Mn Reaction

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Polarography of the Manganese has been studied in various supporting electrolytes in the light of effect of successive cations from the series of alkali-metals and effect of anions. The kinetic parameters have been calculated by Koryta's method. The decrease of rate constant (k^0) was observed with the increase in the radius of the alkali metal ions and tetra alkyl cation. The rate constant was found to increase in the order $\text{I} > \text{Br} > \text{Cl} > \text{ClO}_4^-$, when anions are changed. The decrease in rate with cation has been explained on the increase of radius of the cation and increase of rate constant due to change of anions is due to the accelerating effect of halide ions.

It was assumed for the application of the Nernst equation to the oxidation-reduction reaction at the electrode that electrochemical equilibrium is achieved at the electrode, but there are cases in which the equilibrium is slow to attain. The interpretation of such electrode process involves kinetic considerations. The derivation of the current potential relationship for the electrode process has helped much in the understanding of the kinetics of electrode reactions.

The theory of the irreversible waves was first developed by Eyring and coworkers¹ and Tanaka and Tamamushi², but a more rigorous treatment was made independently by several workers. Among these methods may be mentioned those of Delahay³, Koutecky⁴, Tachi⁵, Randles⁶, Matsuda⁷, Gellings⁸ and Koryta¹¹.

The analysis of irreversible polarographic waves as proposed by Matsuda and Gellings and Koryta merits further discussion and application, because in this form these seem to be the easy methods for calculating the kinetic parameters for the general case when the rate of the backward reaction is significant; *i.e.*, for a quasi-reversible (or partially irreversible) polarographic wave.

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If the magnitude of the rate constant K_s lies within the limits $2 \times 10^{-2} > K_s > 5 \times 10^{-5}$ cm/sec. the reactions are termed quasireversible⁹⁻¹⁰. The method of determining the rate constant for a quasireversible electrode process is described in detail by Matsuda and Ayabe¹⁰. Their relationship are fairly complicated. Koryta¹¹ gives a simpler modified method.

The polarographic reduction of manganese has been studied by a number of workers¹²⁻¹⁵, but detailed study of the kinetic parameters of the electrode reaction has not been reported. The effect of halide ions and temperature has been studied by the authors¹⁶ by Matsuda and Gellings method. The present paper describes results of the effect of cations and anions of the supporting electrolytes on the kinetics of discharge of Manganese ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

An LP 55 Heyrovsky system polarograph was used manually. The dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics : $m = 1.40$ mg/sec. and $t(\text{droptime}) = 4.6$ secs. in $0.1M$ NaClO_4 solution at -1.5 volts vs. S.C.E. (saturated calomel electrode).

Solution of $\text{Mn}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ was prepared by precipitating the Manganese carbonate from AR : Manganese sulphate and then dissolving the carbonate in requisite amount of dilute perchloric acid. Standard solutions of lithium chloride, sodium chloride, potassium chloride, cesium chloride, sodium perchlorate, sodium bromide, sodium iodide and tetra methyl ammonium bromide were prepared and used as supporting electrolytes. Gelatin (0.005%) was used as maxima suppressor. All the experiments were carried out at constant temperature of 30° maintained by means of Haake type ultra thermostat. The dissolved oxygen was expelled by passing purified nitrogen through the solution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Manganese gives a single well defined wave in all the supporting electrolytes. The reduction is diffusion controlled and quasireversible. The kinetic parameters have been calculated by using Koryta's method. The brief outline of the method is given below :

According to Weber and Koutecky, the following relation holds for mean currents,

$$i_{\text{irrev}} = i_{\text{rev}} F(x) \quad (1)$$

where

$$X = \sqrt{\frac{12}{7}} \left(\frac{k_f}{\sqrt{D}} + \frac{k_b}{\sqrt{D'}} \right) \sqrt{t} \quad (2)$$

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The mean current predicted by equation (1) may be expressed by the approximate equation

$$i_{\text{irrev}} = i_{\text{rev}} \frac{0.886 \left(\frac{k_f}{\sqrt{D}} + \frac{k_b}{\sqrt{D'}} \right) \sqrt{t}}{1 + 0.886 \left(\frac{k_f}{\sqrt{D}} + \frac{k_b}{\sqrt{D'}} \right) \sqrt{t}} \quad (3)$$

where k_f and k_b are formal rate constants for forward and backward processes and D and D' are diffusion coefficients of oxidised and reduced respectively and are regarded as equal.

From equation (3)

$$\frac{i_{\text{irrev}}}{i_{\text{rev}} - i_{\text{irrev}}} = 0.886 (k_f D^{-1/2} + k_b D'^{-1/2}) \sqrt{t} \quad (4)$$

We may write for the rate constants of reduction k_f and of oxidation k_b referred to the reversible half wave potential E_{r_1} ,

$$k_f = k^0 \sqrt{\left(\frac{D}{D'}\right)^{\alpha}} \exp \left[\frac{-\alpha n F (E - E_{r_1})}{RT} \right] \quad (5)$$

$$k_b = k^0 \sqrt{\left(\frac{D'}{D}\right)^{1-\alpha}} \exp \left[\frac{(1-\alpha) n F (E - E_{r_1})}{RT} \right] \quad (6)$$

Fig. 1 :—Determination of k^0 and α . Plot of $\log i/(i_a - i)$ Vs $E_{a.s}$ for 1 mM Mn^{2+} in 0.1M CsCl at 30°.

We denote the current corresponding to the reversible half wave potential E_{r_1} as i' . On substituting for k_f and k_b at $E = E_{r_1}$ we obtain from equation (4)

$$k^0 = \frac{i}{(i_{\text{rev}} - i')} \frac{\sqrt{D' \alpha D^{(1-\alpha)}}}{2 \times 0.886 \sqrt{t}} \quad (7)$$

The value i_{rev} is $\frac{1}{2}i_d$ at $E = E_{r\frac{1}{2}}$ so that the final formula for k^0 reads as follows :

$$k^0 = \frac{i_l}{(i_d - 2i')} \frac{\sqrt{D'\alpha D^{(1-\alpha)}}}{0.886 \sqrt{t}} \quad (8)$$

Taking $D = D'$ for most of the cases

$$k^0 = \frac{i'}{(i_d - 2i')} \frac{\sqrt{D}}{.886 \sqrt{t}} \quad (9)$$

The method for determining k^0 and α from a cathodic wave is seen from Fig. (1). At sufficiently positive potentials i practically equal to i_{rev} , so that asymptote drawn from $E \rightarrow \infty$ crosses the potential axis at the reversible half wave potential ($E_{r\frac{1}{2}}$). The value of α is determined from the slope of the asymptote drawn from the negative branch of the curve at sufficiently negative potentials where $k_f \gg k^0$ and $i_{\text{rev}} = i_d$.

Thus the values of k^0 and α were determined from equation (9) and slope of log plot sufficiently negative potential in various electrolytes at 30°.

TABLE I

Effect of Cations

1mM Mn²⁺ in 0.1M Supporting Electrolyte at 30°

Cation	i_d μA	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -volt vs S.C.E.	$E_{r\frac{1}{2}}$ -volt vs S.C.E.	$D \times 10^3$ cm ² /sec	$\alpha\eta$	$k^0 \times 10^3$ cm/sec.
Lithium	5.35	1.478	1.475	2.84	1.6	9.5
Sodium	5.34	1.478	1.475	2.84	1.6	9.5
Potassium	5.38	1.480	1.476	2.86	1.5	6.75
Cesium	5.34	1.486	1.482	2.88	1.5	6.50
Tetraalkyl (Tetramethyl)	5.18	1.535	1.525	2.83	1.27	3.11

Table I shows the values of rate constants and transfer coefficients for 0.1M supporting electrolytes (LiCl, KCl, CsCl and (CH₃)₄NBr). The decrease of the rate constants of the electrode reaction in electrolytes containing successively cations from the series of alkali metals is due to the increasing radius of the alkali metal cations. The sequence of the increase in radius is in fair agreement with the decrease in rate constants which are in the order of Li⁺ > Na⁺ > K⁺ > Cs⁺. The tetra alkyl ammonium cations, which are specifically absorbed in the interface electrode/solution, exert a strong retarding effect on the rate of the electrode reaction of manganese ions and thus rate of the electrode reaction decreases from 9.5 × 10⁻³ cm/sec. in NaCl to 3.1 × 10⁻³ in tetra alkyl bromide. The decrease may also be due to complex formation of metal with Br⁻ as revealed by the negative shift of half way potential from NaClO₄ to (CH₃)₄NBr. Moreover it is also possible that these specifically absorbed particles may block the electrode surface¹⁷ and hence retard the rate. This effect of alkyl ions has been more pronounced in the case of nickel¹⁸ and cobalt¹⁹.

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TABLE II

Effect of Anions

1mM Mn²⁺ in 0.1M Supporting Electrolyte at 30°

Anion	α_n	K° cm/sec.
Perchlorate	1.4	9.8×10^{-3}
Chloride	1.45	9.4×10^{-3}
Bromide	1.45	1.35×10^{-2}
Iodide	1.5	1.6×10^{-2} (Reversible).

To see the effect of anions on the electrode reaction, polarography of the Mn^{2+} was studied in sodium perchlorate, chloride, bromide and iodide as supporting electrolytes (0.1M). It is observed that the rate constant increases as we pass from ClO_4^- to I^- and in 0.1M NaI it is practically reversible as seen from the rate constant given in Table II. The accelerating effect of halide ions and in particular iodide ions has been discussed in our previous communication¹⁶ on the assumption of (1) adsorption of halide ions at the dropping mercury electrode surface and (2) that the rate determining step is the formation in the bulk solution of an activated iodide complex that takes part in the electrode reaction with a higher rate than free Mn^{2+} ions.

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